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PASALTHA CHAWMA: THE (UN)FORGOTTEN HERO

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In Mizo traditional society, *pasaltha*¹ occupied an important and reputable position by dint of their talent and ability exclusively in terms of warfare and hunting. There were many famous *pasaltha* who were well known amongst the Mizo community as a whole till day. Meanwhile, due to limited sources and lesser attention in the writing of Mizo historical narratives, there could also be least known Mizo *pasaltha* who too did achieve great success and played important roles for their chiefs and for their villages. As the famous George Orwell rightly highlighted, “History is written by the winners”,² marginalization of historical accounts can be seen in the history of Mizo heroes and warriors as well. Out of numerous forgotten *pasaltha*, the story of Chawma, a warrior in Bengkhuaia’s village, who was said to have killed James Winchester and captured his young daughter Mary Winchester (Zoluti), can also be accounted in Mizo historical narrative.

Chawma- A Pasaltha

Pasaltha Chawma’s real name was Chhungchungnunga; he was given a nickname Chemchawma due to his good

physical body structure, and his fellow villagers called him in short form, Chawma. When the Chief Bengkhuaia and his ally raided Cachar district on January 23, 1871, Chawma was said to be one of the bravest warriors. On that raid at Alexandrapur's tea garden, Chawma killed James Winchester, a planter in the tea garden and taken his young daughter Mary Winchester (Zoluti) as a captive. T.H. Lewin mentioned about this incident:

“They [The Lushai/Lusei] had committed a series of forays of the most aggravated character in the neighbouring district of Cachar, killing several Europeans, and carrying off Mary Winchester, the little daughter of a planter, with many other British native subjects, into captivity.”³

This raid was not a very common event in the history of Mizoram when the chiefs assembled together to fight a common enemy because though the Mizo chiefs, who were independent and sovereign chiefs, were fighting against each other, they rarely made a confederation to fight against a common enemy. But this happened when the Western Mizo chiefs fought against the British in 1870.⁴ It is said that when the raiding party returned to their village, some of his fellow hunters wanted to depose Mary Winchester on the way perhaps because taking a girl child was burdensome to them. But Chawma, being a childless father, rejected the pressure from his fellow men; instead he gave protection to the young slave girl and safely brought her to their village. Even when they reached their village, he kept the young girl Mary Winchester (who was given a Mizo name, 'Zoluti') in his home for quite some time but he later surrendered her to the Chief Bengkhuaia for a good reason. Pi Rozingi, the

grandniece of Chawma who died at the age of 100 years in 2002 A.D at Sialsuk, said that as Zoluti was having white skin and white hairs, Chawma considered that it was not good for him to keep her. Thus, after keeping the girl in Kawlri for a while, Chawma brought her to Bengkhuaia's house at Sailam. She remained a captive in Bengkhuaia's house till the British army expedition team took her back in 1871.⁵

On a less serious tone, after killing James Winchester, Chawma took away James Winchester's wristwatch but he did not know what it exactly was. When they reached a safer place, he took it out from his pocket, checked it out and listened the ticking sound of the watch. As he never seen such kind of device before, he thought that it might be some tool for witchcraft or some bad omen. He did not like to keep it and threw it away to Tlawng river. When later he saw the British Army personnel wearing such kind of watch, he realized that it was a wristwatch and he greatly regretted on losing such valuable item.

When the Mizos heard a rumour that the British government sent 'punitive' expedition (The Lushai Expedition 1871-72) to the Lushai hills and punished many of the chiefs responsible for the raids, Chawma and his family were also apprehensive of the reaction from the British. Keeping in mind the awful risk for Chawma's life, his wife's nephew Khumawna⁶ was willing to show sympathy by daring to take all the responsibilities for his uncle Chawma. He told his uncle Chawma, "The British may kill or imprison you; if they do so, my auntie would be too lonesome since you have no children. I have seven kids, and they will do fine without me. So, I will take the responsibility of killing

James Winchester and for capturing Mary Winchester. I will sacrifice my life for you.” Then, Khumawna owned up the responsibility and was known then as the killer of James Winchester and captivator of Mary Winchester.

Being a killer of a British subject, and for capturing Mary Winchester, Chawma’s life was not secure after the British conquest. As such, he lived a secluded life, and his stories are also buried even during his lifetime. It is said that he was living a secreted life, and refused to reveal his real identity to remain alive. Thus, very little is known about him after the Mizo chiefs were subdued by the British. It is said that he died of *ngawr natna* (tuberculosis) at the age of 90 on May 7, 1915 at Kawlri. As he was a childless father, he died under the safe arms of his brother’s step-daughter Thanghnuaii (W/o. Dolenga). He was buried at *tianghran thlan* (which was considered an exclusive grave dug for warrior and heroes). The descendants of his relatives tried to find out his tombstone at the abandoned Kawlri village but they failed. Later years, Chawma’s memorial tombstone was re-erected beside Thanghnuaii’s tomb at the graveyard of Sialsuk village by his relatives.

On Hero - A Paradigm Shift

The intervention of British colonial administration in the frontier region particularly in the non-state space in the then Lushai Hills largely changed the community perception of hero in many ways. In the traditional Mizo society, being a hero or warrior was highly regarded and everyone desired to achieve that status as it promised privileges both in the physical world and in the world to come. But the execution of state administration in the Lushai Hills drastically changed

the perception of hero as the traditional heroes were now considered as 'criminal' and 'unlawful persons' by the colonial government. As the abled native rulers and their warriors often paid heavy prices in their misdeeds under the colonial administration, tagging a person as a hero or a warrior could not longer enjoy the previous privileges. Especially for the family and relatives of *Pasaltha* Chawma, being a traditional hero became a heavy burden for their existence. To worsen the situation, there was a theatre play in 1931 at Aijal (Aizawl) where the raids of Alexandrapur tea garden by Bengkhuaia and the killing of James Winchester and hostage of Mary Winchester by the warriors was shown. While watching the play, the then Superintendent of the Lushai Hills A.G McCall got irritated and called off the show abruptly. He then furiously asked, "Who was the killer of the white man (*Sap*)? Where does he live?" The audience replied him that the culprit was Chawma from abandoned Kawlri village and nobody lived there anymore, even Chawma's whereabouts could not be known. McCall then declared, "Nobody from the descendants of Chawma will be given government jobs from now on."

Under the colonial administration, the situation for warrior like Chawma was growing worse and misfortunes befell on him and his relatives. For many years Chawma's near relatives did not dare to apply government jobs as they feared that McCall's words might affect them. To avoid maltreatment from the government and the public, some of Chawma's relative also migrated to Burma from Lushai Hills. Soon after the show at Aijal Theater, Chawma's brother's step-daughter Thanghnuaii was informed by their village chief to vacate their house as he wanted to construct a new

house in the same plot. It was an indirect assault to Thanghnuaii for her relationship with Chawma, and she and her families were compelled to migrate reluctantly to Sialsuk village.

Even after her demise, Thanghnuaii's descendants continued to keep the secret, and the spear (*Fei*) and a short sword (*Kawlnam/Chempui*) of Chawma that he used for killing James Winchester also continued to be the hidden possession of the family. As their families were facing many hardships in the previous times, they were never likely to reveal that they were still preserving Chawma's weapons. It is only after many years passed that Chawma's spear and short sword are publicly revealed by his grandchildren that are still safely kept. For the record, Chawma's weapons are presently preserved by his grand son-in-law Mr. H. Lalngilneia, Kulikawn, Aizawl.

The Hero turned Victim

As mentioned earlier, *pasaltha* enjoyed a privilege position in every village in the Mizo traditional society. Killing enemies and carrying off slaves were the utmost wishes of every male member of the society. If a male member in the society did not kill animals or carried off human heads, he could not attain reputed position among his peers and could not attain *pialral* in his life after death. Their daring spirits comforted their village against enemies and wild animals. Even for the chiefs having fearless *pasaltha* was a thing to be proud off and much needed. For the *pasaltha* himself killing or taking captive of their enemy was a good opportunity for attaining the high status in the physical world as well as in life after death. When the British

colonial government started their penetration in the then Lushai Hills, *Pasaltha* Chawma became a victim for being a hero or a warrior; for him such events became a mere nightmare. Because of colonial intervention in his land, he could no longer avail privileges that he was entitled in the traditional society.

Based on the life story of *Pasaltha* Chawma, we could surmise that the position of a hero in the traditional Mizo society has undergone change; in fact, it was deeply downscaled by the colonial intervention. In some discourses, British colonialism was stressed as a blessing for the isolated tribes as they brought forward modernity and scientific advancements. It may be right in some aspect, but for the heroes of the Mizo, it is a total disaster. It can be related with the renowned Rudyard Kipling's poem – 'the white man's burden'⁷ because their heroic actions and activities now turned them to be criminals and offenders.

In conclusion, it can be said that *Pasaltha* Chawma tried his best to protect his land and hunting ground of the Mizo chiefs against the intruders. In traditional Mizo society, there was a kind of a division of labour- some are blacksmith, some are healer, etc.; for *pasaltha*, their duty was to protect their villages and land from the intruders. Likewise, *Pasaltha* Chawma also did his role faithfully for his chief and the entire community. Daring to sacrifice his life, he attacked the enemies and captured little girl as per their normal practice, and spared his life. He did all such daring actions for the protection of his native land from the enemies. For him, showing his bravery was the fulfillment of his highest responsibility for being a warrior of Chief Bengkhuaia and his village.

The question that remains here is that even in modern nation state the recipients of the military gallantry medals are mostly the persons who killed their enemies or sacrificed their lives in the warzone; and why should traditional heroes be labeled as criminals and habitually being marginalized from the mainstream historical accounts.

Chawma's spear (*Fei*) and short sword (*Kawlnam/Chempui*) that he used in killing James Winchester, it is preserved by Mr. H. Lalngilneia, Kulikawn, Aizawl.

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- 2 <http://alexpeak.com/twr/hiwbtw/> accessed on 12 September 2016.
- 3 TH Lewin, *A Fly on The Wheel or How I Helped to Govern India*, Tribal Research Institute, Aizawl, 2005 (Reprint), p.25.
- 4 Rohmingmawii, "Bengkhuia (1825-1879)", *Historical Journal Mizoram*, Volume XI, November 2010, p.38.
- 5 Interviewed with Mr. H Lalngilneia (Grand Son-in-law of Chawma) at his residence, Kulikawn, Aizawl on 28th November, 2016.
- 6 Khumawna's son bears the name 'Mingothatlana' which may be translated as 'the one who killed white man'. H. Lalvenhima, "Zoluti Mantu Ka Pu Chawma Fei leh Kawlnam hi" in *Meichher*, Aizawl, 2015.
- 7 Rudyard Kipling, *Rudyard Kipling's Verse: Definitive Edition*, London: Hodder & Stoughton, 1949.